

GANG SCHEDULING ALGORITHM FOR RECONFIGURABLE COMPUTING SYSTEMS

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Abstract: The Reconfigurable computing system is emerging as one of the efficient architecture that gives better performance and at the same time dynamically adapts to the needs of the environment. The success of the Reconfigurable system mainly depends on the efficient scheduling of tasks to be executed in the reconfigurable hardware. The scheduling algorithms used in general purpose operating systems have been designed for software based tasks or processes and needs to be modified to suit the dynamic nature of the reconfigurable systems. In this paper Gang scheduling algorithm, an algorithm used for scheduling jobs in parallel computer architecture is taken and adapted to meet the needs of the reconfigurable systems. The performance of the four algorithms namely, static scheduling, first come first serve, shortest job first and Gang scheduling were simulated and the results were compared. It has been found that the Gang scheduling algorithm provides almost 100 % utilization of the slots, reduces the waiting time and provides a fair scheduling to reduce the execution times of jobs with long execution times.

Keywords: *Reconfigurable computing, Operating system scheduling, Gang scheduling*

I. INTRODUCTION

Data processing plays a very vital role in any computing applications across all sections and technical domains. This in turn requires a significant improvement in the execution time which is unfortunately possible when the traditional computing systems where general purpose CPU is involved. Reconfigurable computing systems(RCS) with Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) as accelerators provide the necessary computing power with less electrical power requirement and has become one of the interesting research areas [1]-[2].

Reconfigurable Computing Systems offer a number of advantages in terms of execution speed, speedup, power, reprogrammability and reconfigurability due to the programmable architecture of FPGAs and in built functional blocks such as arithmetic and DSP blocks. Since all the blocks of the programmable hardware operate simultaneously their speedup is much higher in a number of applications [3]-[8].

This paper explores the various scheduling policies available in conventional operating systems which can be modified to suit the needs of the reconfigurable computing systems. Section 2 presents a brief introduction to the merits of RCS. The various scheduling algorithms widely used in conventional operating systems are discussed in section 3 with special reference to the Gang scheduling. Section 4 explains the details of the research work carried out with reference to Gang scheduling and their suitability to reconfigurable computing. Section 5 presents a summary of the discussions and suggests future directions.

2. RECONFIGURABLE COMPUTING

The reconfigurable system allows allows the architecture to be customized based on the needs. A number of industrial applications ranging from edge computing to cloud computing have employed FPGAs as accelerators and re-configurable modules to improve their performance [9-12]. Developing a software for an application is more more faster than developing a hardware based system as hardware synthesis is time consuming.

A practical solution is to modify the operating systems with standard interfaces to provide a unified view for developers and users so that the CPUs and FPGAs can be used together to get the benefits of both processors [13]. The FPGAs can be reconfigured any number of times to deploy a number of modules and thus extending the usability of the hardware. Figure 1. gives an idea about implementing various algorithms such as encryption, image processing and signal processing applications on the same reconfigurable hardware [14]. The FPGAs have been found to speedup the execution in a number of applications such as Networking, signal processing, image processing, video processing, automotive computing, aerospace applications and cryptography

applications. The FPGAs of recent times have the capability of Partial reconfiguration. Partial reconfiguration allows a predefined portion of an FPGA to be reconfigured without disturbing the remaining part of the device. This extends the capability of the applications.

OPERATING SYSTEM DESIGN CHALLENGES

In any computing system, the operating system plays a major role in controlling the hardware and the I/O interfaces. The success of the design mainly depends on the efficient controlling of the hardware by the OS. The conventional operating systems are designed for general purpose CPUs and not designed for the Reconfigurable Computing systems.

The OS need to be customised in terms of balancing the workload of the CPUs and the reconfigurable hardware which is the main job of the Scheduler. This paper analyses various conventional scheduling algorithms such as First come First Serve(FCFS), Shortest Job First (SJF) and Priority Based Scheduling. The Gang Scheduling algorithm, which is used in Parallel Computing systems is also implemented and all these algorithms were compared. The suitability of these algorithms for RCS is discussed and a novel scheduling algorithm suitable for RCS is proposed.

Fig 1. Reconfigurable Computing

The operating system is responsible for task scheduling, resource management and time management. In a RCS, the operating system should manage the reconfigurable hardware and its peripherals also. Figure 2. shows the different modules of OS which run on CPU and FPGA [15]. The major challenge for the operating system is to properly schedule the task which have to run on CPU and FPGA. They have to be properly synchronized in order to improve the execution time and minimize the waiting time. In order to achieve this a suitable scheduling policy should be selected. In this paper, the suitability of conventional scheduling policies have been implemented and tested.

Because of the nature of the reconfigurable hardware, several configurations are possible for the same application. For example, in an encryption application, in the Electronic Code Book (ECB) mode, several blocks can be encrypted simultaneously based on the availability of the slots in the FPGA. This speeds up the execution of the application. Hence when a number of applications have to be executed in the programmable hardware and the number of available slots also varies at different instances of time, the operating system has to manage different sets of configurations. This is the main challenge for the operating system’s scheduling policies.

3. A brief insight into Scheduling Algorithms

3.1 First Come First Served (FCFS)

An incoming task which is to be executed by a CPU will be placed in a First In First Out (FIFO) queue. The tasks will be executed in the order in which they arrive at the queue. The performance is measured in terms of average waiting time and it is calculated based on the arrival time and burst time. It is a non-preemptive algorithm and the Average Waiting Time is not optimal. Also in FCFS, the resources cannot be used in parallel. FCFS is an idealistic scheduling algorithm

3.2 Shortest Job First (SJF)

The scheduler searches for the job with the shortest burst time among the jobs available in the queue and executes it first. This algorithm can be used for both non preemptive and preemptive scheduling processes. This algorithm gives priority to the execution of shortest jobs and avoid them from waiting for a long time due to the execution of jobs with longer execution times. In this algorithm, the waiting time is less for shorter jobs and longer for jobs with longer burst times.

Slot 1	A1		A2		A3		A4		A5	
Slot 2		B1			B2				B3	
Slot 3	C1					C2				
Slot 4	D1						D2			
a. Static Configuration										
Slot 1	A1		A4		B2			C2		
Slot 2		A2			C1				A8	
Slot 3	B1		A5		A6	B3			A9	
Slot 4		A3	D1			A7		B4		
b. SJF Configuration										
Slot 1	A1		A2		B2			C3		
Slot 2		B1				C2				
Slot 3	C1				A3		D2			
Slot 4	D1						B3			A4
c. FCFS Configuration										

Fig 3. Examples of implementation of Scheduling algorithms

3.3 Round Robin Scheduling

The CPU’s time is divided into a number of time slices of equal duration. Every job will be given one time slice for execution. At the end of the time slice the job will exit even if it is not complete, saving the intermediate results and once again join at the tail of the queue to get the next time slice. In this algorithm all the jobs will be executed in a round robin fashion and the last job in the queue need not wait for a long time to start its execution. In this algorithm, each job has to be preempted at the end of the time slice, after saving the intermediate results. In a hardware, since all the blocks will be executing in parallel, storing the intermediate results is very difficult and hence this algorithm is not suitable for hardware implementations.

3.4 Priority Scheduling

In this algorithm, each job in the queue will be assigned a priority number; smaller the number higher the priority. The job with the highest priority will be executed first preempting the execution of the lower priority job if any. Hence, low priority jobs will be preempted whenever higher priority jobs join the queue. This leads to increased waiting time for low priority jobs, which is known as starvation. Starvation of low priority jobs can be minimized by increasing its priority level based on its waiting time; this concept is known as aging.

3.5. Gang Scheduling

Gang scheduling is another popular algorithm which deals with the scheduling strategies deployed for related threads which are supposed to be executed simultaneously on different CPUs. Interestingly, these threads can be from the same process or may belong to different processes dealing with different data sets and applications. Gang scheduling is one of the popular scheduling algorithms in parallel computing architecture.

Slot 1	A1		A2		A3		A4		A5	
Slot 2	B1			B2				B3		
Slot 3	C1					C2				
Slot 4	D1						D2			
a. Static Configuration										
Slot 1	A1	B1	D1	A2	B3	D2	A3	B5	D3	A4
Slot 2	C1	B1	D1	C2	B3	D2	C3	B5	D3	C4
Slot 3	C1	B2	D1	C2	B4	D2	C3	B6	D3	C4
Slot 4	C1	B2	D1	C2	B4	D2	C3	B6	D3	C4
b. GANG Scheduling										

Fig.4. A typical implementation- Static vs Gang scheduling

4. Popular OS Scheduler Implementations

Given the fact that the Operating system has to handle different kinds of tasks, a single scheduling algorithm can meet the needs of all the tasks and their priorities or requirements. Hence the popular operating systems use a combination of different scheduling algorithms.

For example, the Windows operating system uses a multilevel feedback queue (MLFQ), which is a combination of first in first out, round-robin and fixed priority with preemptive scheduling, and Mac Operating system deploys a multilevel feedback queue with priority bands for threads. The prioritization will be in the order of real-time, kernel mode only, system high priority and normal. It also employs preemptive scheduling on the threads.

Linux Operating System also uses MLFQ with priority levels from 0 to 140. Levels 0–99 are reserved for realtime tasks and 100–140 are considered nice task levels. It uses “Completely Fair Scheduling” based on the Rotating Staircase Deadline strategy. This fair queuing process scheduler is greatly used in most of the operating systems. Solaris Operating system also deploys a similar scheduling discipline with different levels and priorities.

From the above it is clear that only a combination of different scheduling algorithms along with priority levels can make an efficient scheduler. Only this inference encouraged us to propose a Novel Scheduling algorithm for the reconfigurable computing systems.

CASE STUDY

In the reconfigurable computing system, a number of partially reconfigurable slots are assumed. Two concepts which are used in the general purpose architecture based computing systems were adapted to suit our needs. First, the multi server queuing model is assumed. The model is represented by the notation,

A/B/c/N/K where

A - the inter arrival-time distribution, Usually Markov, Exponential distribution

B - the service time distribution,

c - number of parallel servers

N - system capacity

K - represents the size of the calling population

N, K are usually dropped, if they are infinity

The Gang scheduling algorithm used in parallel computing systems is the next concept adapted to suit the needs of RCS.

Since an algorithm implemented in hardware can not be preempted during an intermediate time, the conventional algorithms were tested in the non-preemptive mode only. A sample data set with random values of burst time and arrival time and priority was created. The synthetic data consisted of 200 jobs. Static scheduling, First Come First Serve (FCFS), Shortest Job First (SJF) and modified Gang scheduling algorithm were tested using the given data set. The jobs were grouped into four categories;

1. Low priority Jobs with short execution times (A)
2. High priority Jobs with short execution times (B)
3. Low priority Jobs with long execution times (C)
4. High priority Jobs with long execution times (D)

The results of the simulation were compared. The Reconfigurable hardware is assumed to have four slots which can be reconfigured independently. Also to simplify the tasks only four types of jobs were selected as mentioned earlier. The waiting time for all these four algorithms has been presented in Fig.5. It is assumed that in the static configuration each slot is configured for a specific application/job, for example, encryption or image processing application. The slots allotted for short execution jobs (A and B) were idle after each execution. The waiting time is more for jobs with long execution times as they can not utilize the slots which were reserved for jobs a and B. In FCFS implementation, all the jobs were given the same priority and hence the waiting time is uniform for all the jobs. In Shortest Job First (SJF) implementation, the waiting time is much less for short jobs and very high for the jobs with long execution times. In Gang Scheduling, it is assumed that each job can be divided into a number of sub-blocks and can be executed independently without any constraints. The scheduler arranges the jobs in such a way that no slot is left free by properly arranging the jobs in the available slots. From the graph in Figure 5, it is clear that the Gang Scheduler gives a fair treatment for short as well as long jobs and the over all waiting time is much less compared to other scheduling algorithms.

Fig. 5. Waiting time in queue for the Jobs

Fig. 6. Execution time

The time taken to execute different jobs in the reconfigurable slots is shown in Figure 6. In the case of static, FCS and SJF configurations, the jobs are not divided into sub blocks and they are executed in the available slots during their turn. On the other hand the Gang scheduling algorithm, divides the jobs into sub blocks and executes them in parallel. For example, if the burst time of a job is 80 time units, it will take 80 time units to get executed in any of the available slots in the other three algorithms. Whereas in Gang Scheduling algorithm, it will be divided into 8 sub blocks of 10 time units each and simultaneously executed in all the four slots in two batches of 10 units each. Hence the execution time will be only 20 time units instead of 80 time units. This reduces the execution time of the jobs with long execution times. Also the slot utilization is can be achieved to be around 100 % in SJF and Gang Scheduling as shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Slot utilization in percentage

5. Conclusion and Future Work

Reconfigurable computing systems are employed in every possible domain from edge computing to the cloud computing. High speed, low power, quick prototyping and reconfigurability are some of the main reasons for the success of the RCS. In this paper, we have proposed a modified Gang scheduling algorithm, which can reduce the waiting time, improve the slot utilization and execution time and fairness to both short and long execution time jobs. In future, we plan to employ the popular schemes such as Multi level Feedback queue along with the proposed algorithm to design better scheduling algorithms to meet the growing and complex needs of the Reconfigurable computing systems.

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